

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B118
Date: 03 Aug 2005
Take Off: 10:02:59
Landing: 14:58:32
Flight Time: 4h55m33s

Campaign: AMPEP
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: South and East Coast, to Newcastle area

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Eiko Nemitz	CEH
5	Flight Manager	Stephen Devereau	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	Filters	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	Core Chemistry/CCM2	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
9	NO _x	Andy MacDonald	UEA
10	AMS	Hugh Coe	Manchester University
11	AMS Training	Gerard Capes	Manchester University
12	PTRMS	Anne Hulse	UEA
13	WAS/PAN	Ruth Boddy	York University
14	Bag sampling 1	Daniela Famulari	CEH
15	Bag sampling 2	Debbie Polson	CEH
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B118 Track 03-AUG-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B118

Date: 3rd August 2005

Project: AMPEP

Location: South coast - Dover - East Coast

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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094521		Start posn	0.00 kft	124	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
093854		INU to Nav	0.13 kft	124	
095501		start taxi	0.13 kft	124	
100259		T/O	0.0 kft		
100753		asp open	9.0 kft	048	
110200	111542	Profile 1	8.0 - 0.05 kft		
110325	110518	Run 1	6.0 kft	136	
110650	110818	Run 2	4.0 kft	129	
111041	111144	Run 3	2.0 kft	131	
111333	111442	Run 4	0.5 kft	119	
111605	111719	Run 5	0.1 kft	066	
111727	111843	Profile 2	0.1 - 1.0 kft	068	
111844	132820	Run 6	0.10 kft	074	
113009		surface P 1026	0.69 kft	075	
115726		surface P 1023	0.72 kft	054	
123010		surface P 1022	0.78 kft	004	
125422		surface P 1021	0.77 kft	324	
132648		surface P 1019	0.85 kft	326	
133106	133207	Run 7	0.10 kft	168	
133213	133752	Profile 3	0.03 - 4.6 kft	173	
133404		interrupt P3	1.8 kft	168	
133404	133519	Run 8	1.9 kft	173	
133519		restart P3	1.9 kft	173	
133802	133854	Run 9	4.7 - 4.6 kft	153	
134012	134412	Profile 4	4.6 - 0.87 kft	141	
134412	142027	Run 10	0.87 - 0.80 kft	148	
135410		surface P 1021	0.84 kft	157	
145832		Land	0.12 kft	352	
150313		final posn.	0.10 kft	310	

B118 Track 03-AUG-05

Sortie Brief: AMPEP

Flight Number : B118

Mission Scientist: Eiko Nemitz, CEH

Date : 03-August-2005

Outline schedule:

07:00 – Power to aircraft – warm-up
09:00 – Briefing
10:15 – Clear aircraft and security check
10:30 – Doors close
11:00 – Take off Cranfield
15:30 – Land Cranfield
16:00 – Debrief
17:30 – Power down

Location: A coastal transect of the South and East Coast of England

Sortie Aims: To measure the UK pollutant budget of a range of gases and aerosols leaving the UK in gentle North Westerly airflow over the UK. The objective, in addition to measuring the export fluxes of pollutants is to derive the chemical processing (gas/aerosol partitioning & oxidation state) of the air mass.

Sortie Summary: The budget measurements will be obtained by flying off the South and East coasts along a coastal transect beginning in the Bristol Channel to sample background air off the coast of Cornwall. The transect of the UK outflow begins along the English Channel heading East to Dover then North to the point where airflow off the land stops, which according to current forecasts is North Yorkshire. Then after refueling (in Inverness) to return along the same East coast path to WP 40 off the Norfolk coast, returning to Cranfield. Vertical profiles (50 – 6000 ft) once upwind in the Bristol channel and downwind of the source region off the S Scottish coast on the Southbound leg will provide the vertical structure in concentration and meteorology. These should clearly extend into the free troposphere (Mission Scientist to verify from profiles of humidity, temperature and CO. These measurements will establish the upwind concentration, the concentration differential at the top of the boundary layer and the concentration in the outflow from the source region. Flight ceiling will be 10000ft. Cabin pressure will be maintained at 1200ft, to minimize expansion of the Tedlar bags.

Sortie Detail with approx timing

- a) Take off Cranfield 09:00 and climb to 10000 ft for transit east to operating area. Destination waypoint 47 in the Bristol Channel; background filter run (sampling) & NO_x calibration.
- b) T+20: Upwind profile down to define the boundary layer structure off the coast with 1 min sampling at each height (6000, 4000, 2000, 500, 100, 50)
- c) T+35: Return to 1000 ft for sampling..
Start of filter run No 1. Start of Bag sampling (1 bag every min) continue all the way up the east coast. 30-minute filter pack runs from here (called by Mission Scientist)
- d) T+ 200 U-turn in front of Firth of Forth, downwind profile up (50, 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000).
- e) T+ 270 Land Cranfield

Crew List:

1. Pilot 1 - Alan Foster
2. Pilot 2 – Alan Roberts
3. CCM – Sue Angold
4. CCM2/Core Chemistry/TDLAS – Ruth Purvis
5. Cloud Physics – Paul James
6. Flight Manager – Steve Devereau
7. Mission Scientist – Eiko Nemitz
8. Filters- Doug Anderson
9. WAS/PAN – Ruth Boddy
10. Bag Sampling 1 – Daniela Famulari
11. Bag Sampling 2 – Debbie Polson
12. AMS – Hugh Coe
13. AMS Training – Gerard Capes
14. PTRMS – Anne Hulse
15. NOxy – Andy MacDonald

- Transit to Bristol Channel
- Profile down to point 37
- 48 50:50N 4:40W
- 46 50:01N 3:25W
- 45 50:01N 2:00W
- 44 50:40N 1:00W
- 43 50:40N 0:30E
- 42 51:05N 1:30E
- 41 51:53N 1:47E
- 40 52:41N 1:47E
- 39 52:00N 1:30E
- 80 54:05N 0:05E
- 79 50:00N 1:10W
- Next point N of 79?
- 79 50:00N 1:10W
- 80 54:05N 0:05E
- 39 52:00N 1:30E
- Cranfield

Init : Tue,02AUG2005 00Z Valid: Wed,03AUG2005 12Z
10m Wind (kt)

Daten: GFS-Modell des amerikanischen Wetterdienstes
 (C) Wetterzentrale
 www.wetterzentrale.de

Instrumentation strategies & issues:

Filter sampling: Filters will be taken throughout the flight. Filter pack 1 will contain a Teflon filter for trace metal analysis. Filter pack 2 will contain a Teflon prefilter (for major ion analysis), a nylon filter (for HNO₃ & HCl) and an acidified paper filter (for NH₃). Filters will be changed approximately every 30 minutes or when flight conditions change (as advised by the Mission Scientist). Filters are preloaded into cartridges, which need to be handled with gloves and stored in sealed bags immediately. Filter sampling will be suspended during vertical profiles and resumed when FL10 is re-attained. During breaks, filter packs will be isolated by switching off the pump (to minimise evaporation of volatile aerosol components). During initial transfer to the operating area, a set of filters should be loaded into the filter packs, without sampling, to provide a blank value. Three 30-min runs of filters on each leg (S→N and N→S)

AMS: The AMS will be operated continuously during the flight. Monitored masses will include m/z 16, 18, 28, 30, 43, 44, 46, 57 and 64. The inlet remains closed until airborne to minimize contamination during taxi take-off.

Core Chemistry: CO, SO₂, NO and NO₂ will be measured continuously during the flight. CO will be calibrated every 30 minutes at FL10.

Tedlar bags: Tedlar bags will be filled at a flow rate of 6 lpm, filling a bag over a duration of 30 s. Bags will be filled every 3 minutes upwind and every minute downwind of the source region and during each leveling out for a profile step. Bags should be filled to about 90% of their capacity to maximise sample volume. The cabin pressure will be tightly controlled. Bags from first part of flight can be stored in cargo hold for second part.

Aerosol & cloud physics: CN and PCASP are operated continuously.

Core meteorology & state: Are recorded as standard. Video recording of front facing and downfacing cameras.

PTRMS: Operation as normal.

NO_{xy}: Operation as normal; calibration during transits at FL100

WAS: Sampling density and location to be decided.

TDL for CH₄ and CO₂: Operated by FAAM.

Quick-look data: pressure height, lat, long, temp, RH, CN, SO₂, NO, NO₂, O₃, CO, NO_{xy}(HNO₃)

The flight followed the anticipated flight pattern, transiting to the Bristol Channel at FL10, then crossing Cornwall to the south and descending above the Channel. Clear formation of convective cloud was observed over land in the East part of the country, with the cloud cover clearly tracked the coastline. Flying east along the South coast, concentration increased. However, outflow in the SE into the Channel was not observed, in contradiction to the NAME model prediction. Just NE of Dover, the windspeed dropped dramatically and the wind direction changed to easterly flow. This see-breeze effect only lasted for a few minutes (12:25 – 12:35 GMT), before the wind from the west picked up sufficiently, and it is unclear how much of the outflow (and thus UK budget) may have been lost. The plane passed through a couple of brief showers on the east coast, but heavier rain was observed at a distance over land to the west. In general, plumes of CO were considerable, but enhancement of NO_x, and particular of SO₂, was rather low. Washout of the reactive gases and / or convection may be the explanation. The transect from the coast back to Cranfield was complicated by convective, partly thundery cloud and heavy air traffic. This did not affect the science.

For future flights under westerly winds, a better characterization of the background concentration may be possible if we descend above the Bristol Channel and sample in the Bristol channel at the mid boundary layer height (1000 ft). After this flight it occurred to me (again) that U-turns should be flown into the wind in order to avoid sampling of the aircraft exhaust. It was noted that the zeroing button for the filter volumes got stuck on one occasion and the counter did not start with the sampling interval. It appears to be necessary to double-check that the counter starts probably, after zeroing. Very low CN concentrations (e.g. 150 # cm⁻³) were indicated by the FAAM CPC, while the AMS CPC showed concentrations that were 4 to 5 times larger. A comparison of the data from both CPCs is needed to assess whether there is a general problem with the FAAM CPC.

Eiko Nemitz, CEH

WAS : 32 total

Mission Scientist's Log

HTT-111

Flight No **B.118**.....

Date **03/08/2005**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:04	T/O				broken, overcast light cloud base ~ 8000 ft. top ~ 6000 ft
10:23					Intercepting some cloud tops @ FL10
10:14	FP Run Out			FL10 started	- 11:00:20
10:33					Spike in baro data due to resetting of logging system
					Wind direction at FL10 consistently 290-300
11:00					Leaving FL10 for descent.
					WAS samples at 6000, 2000 & 100 ft.
					Intercepting some cloud @ 6000, mostly just above cloud cloud base ~ 4500 - 3000 variable
11:16					possible slip plane in NO ₂ (five slt)
					short-cut from pt 46 → 44
11:18					run at 1000 ft.
11:18	FP run ②				start for ~ 5 mins.
11:20					lowes flts sube start - volume underestimated accuracy?
11:24					wind speed at 1000 ft ~ 280° was ~ 20° at FL10 and 230° at 100 ft. (7 m/s)
11:55	FP run ②				start
12:00					Dove: enhanced slip traffic, but NO ₂ looks like less total? peak associated with brief period of 10 flts?
12:21					wind down to 3 m/s
12:26					low wind speed (1 m/s) @ 1000

low counts?
flts too small
here into wind

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B118

Date : 3/8/05

Operator and contact info : Ruth Purvis (rupu@faam.ac.uk)

Problems with Instruments

CO	None
O₃	None
NO_x	None
SO₂	None
TDLAS	None
WAS	Operated by York

CO Calibrations

A full calibration lasts approx three minutes, it consists of a cal and a zero
Shorter (quick cals) are sometimes done at low level which is calibration only

<u>Time (GMT)</u>	<u>Level</u>	<u>Comments</u>
10:18	FL100	
10:21	FL100	
11:21	1000ft	
11:51	1000ft	
12:21	1000ft	
12:59	1000ft	BAD CAL REPEATED
13:02	1000ft	
13:45	1000ft	Had to restart cal
13:48	1000ft	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B118

Date: 3/8/05

Operator:papj

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G.M.T.	PCASP		Flow for pcasp	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	DRS Time	Conc/cc			Mean R	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	
	20	0.08									Start pl
1101	20	0.08									090
1102	20	0.08	Flow for pcasp 0.4								080
1103	10	0.09	F = 0.5								070
110416	60	0.2	F = 0.5								060
110603	150	0.08	F=0.58								050
110703	170	0.08	F=0.6								040
110914	220	0.08	F=0.6								030
111024	250	0.09	F=0.6								020
111443	180	0.08	F=0.65								010
111844	260	0.08	F=0.64								Start run 6
1120	200	0.08	F=0.64								
1122	200	0.08	F=0.64								
1124	200	0.08	F=0.64								
1126	200	0.08	F=0.64								
1128	240	0.09	F=0.64								
1130	320	0.09	F=0.64								
1132	320	0.09	F=0.64								
1134	320	0.09	F=0.62								
1136	320	0.09	F=0.62								
1138	200	0.08	F=0.62								
1140	200	0.08	F=0.62								
1142	200	0.08	F=0.62								
1144	200	0.08	F=0.62								
1146	150	0.08	F=0.62								
1148	150	0.08	F=0.62								
1150	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1152	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1154	300	0.08	F=0.6								

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B

Date:

Operator:

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
1156	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1158	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1202	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1204	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1206	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1208	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1210	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1212	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1214	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1216	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1218	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1220	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1221	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1222	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1224	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1226	300	0.08	F=0.6								
1228	200	0.08	F=0.6								
1230	200	0.08	F=0.6								
1232	200	0.08	F=0.6								Pcasp heater turned off
1234	200	0.08	F=0.6								
1236	200	0.08	F=0.6								
1238	250	0.09	F=0.6								
1240	280	0.09	F=0.6								
1242	280	0.09	F=0.6								
1244	280	0.09	F=0.6								
1246	240	0.08	F=0.6								
1248	240	0.08	F=0.6								
1250	220	0.08	F=0.6								
1252	220	0.08	F=0.6								
1254	220	0.08	F=0.6								
1256	100	0.08	F=0.6								
1258	100	0.08	F=0.6								

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B

Date:

Operator:

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		Pcasp flow	SID1 Particle Count	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R			Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
1300	100	0.08	0.58								
1302	100	0.08	0.58								
1304	100	0.08	0.58								
1306	100	0.08	0.58								
1308	100	0.08	0.58								
1310	100	0.08	0.58								
1312	100	0.08	0.58								
1314	100	0.08	0.58								
1316	150	0.08	0.58								
1318	150	0.08	0.58								
1320	150	0.08	0.58								
1322	150	0.08	0.58								
1324	150	0.08	0.58								
1326	100	0.08	0.58								
1328	100	0.08	0.58								
132820											End run 6
133106	70	0.08									Run 7
											Start p3
133310	80	0.08									010
											End p3 @020
1334	80	0.08									Start p4
133620	300	0.2									030
133710	70	0.07									040
134250	200	0.1	0.58								020
134412	150	0.08									Start run 10
1346	150	0.08									
1348	150	0.08									
1350	150	0.08									
1352	150	0.08									
1354	150	0.08									
1356	150	0.08									
1358	150	0.08									

WAS Sampling Summary

Flight Number: B118
Date: 03/08/2005

Campaign Name: AMPEP
Operator: R Boddy (York)

Bottle Start Fill Time	Bottle End Fill Time	Bottle Number	Comments	Final Pressure (bar)
			Pre-flight: Case 7 compressed air line leak. Rectified but monitor for future flights. Cases 1, 6 and 7 available today	
~ 10:10			Level at FL100 for cals	(3.08)
~ 11:00			Start profile descent	
11:04:09		-	Start run 1 at 6000 ft	
11:05:15	11:05:45	1	Fast Fill 30 s (NB: When case flushed, pressure on druck ~ 1.06. Seems high??)	3.25
11:05:18		-	End run 1	
11:10:41		-	Start run 3 at 2000 ft	
11:10:45	11:11:15	2	Fast Fill 30 s	3.31
11:11:44		-	End run 3	
11:13:33		-	Start run 4 at 500 ft	
11:14:42		-	End run 4	
11:16:05		-	Start run 5 at 100 ft	
11:16:13	11:16:43	3	Fast Fill 30 s	3.34
11:17:24		-	End run 5	
11:18:44		-	Start run 6 at 1000 ft	
11:30:31	11:31:01	4	Fast Fill 30 s	3.32
11:51:51	11:52:21	5	Fast Fill 30 s	3.32
12:04:26	12:04:56	6	Fast Fill 30 s	3.32
12:22:05	12:22:35	7	Fast Fill 30 s	3.32
12:37:00	12:37:30	8	Fast Fill 30 s	3.32
12:45:11	12:45:41	9	Fast Fill 30 s (core chemistry signalled elevated NOx levels)	3.32
12:48:11	12:48:41	10	Fast Fill 30 s	3.33
12:51:16	12:51:46	11	Fast Fill 30 s	3.32
13:03:05	13:03:35	12	Fast Fill 30 s	3.33
13:15:06	13:15:36	13	Fast Fill 30 s	3.32
13:16:22	13:16:52	14	Fast Fill 30 s	3.32
13:23:53	13:24:23	15	Fast Fill 30 s	3.33
13:28:20		-	End run 6	

13:31:06		-	Start run 7 at 100 ft	
13:31:11	13:31:41	16	Fast Fill 30 s	3.36
13:32:13		-	End run 7	
~13:34		-	Start run 8 at 2000 ft	
13:34:12	13:34:42	17	Fast Fill 30 s	3.30
13:35:00		-	End run 8	
13:38:02		-	Start run 9 at 4800 ft	
13:38:06	13:38:36	18	Fast Fill 30 s	3.20
13:38:54		-	End run 9	
13:40:12		-	Start profile descent	
13:43:49	13:44:19	19	Fast Fill 30 s	3.37
13:44:12		-	Start run 10 at 1000 ft	
13:53:01	13:53:31	20	Fast Fill 30 s	3.32
14:00:42	14:01:12	21	Fast Fill 30 s	3.32
14:02:23	14:02:53	22	Fast Fill 30 s	3.32
14:08:49	14:09:19	23	Fast Fill 30 s	3.33
14:11:34	14:12:04	24	Fast Fill 30 s	3.32
14:18:24	14:18:54	57	Fast Fill 30 s	3.33
14:20:27		-	End run 10	
~ 14:27		-	FL100 for calcs	
14:27:44	14:28:14	58	Fast Fill 30 s	3.01
14:40:48	14:41:18	59	Fast Fill 30 s	2.98

Flight No. B102Route Antidote *wise circumnavigation
Eng Land & Wales*Date 14-06-05Take Off 8:45Bag Samplers: Dobie / UKSheet No. 1

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
8:05					
08-516	8:08	8:08			
08-516	08:10:20	08:10:49			above clouds.
05-047	08:14:15	14:47			"
246	08:18:00	18:31			"
489	08:22:04	18:25			
364	08:26:00	26:23			
494 489	08:28:20	29:50			Profile 1
051	08:30:20	30:38			"
406	08:32:00	32:28			"
441	08:34:00	34:28			in cloud
048	08:36:00	36:26			below cloud 1000
427	08:37:00	37:28			"
044	08:38:00	38:30			End of profile + 1000 feet
310	08:40:00	40:30			
435	08:42:00	40:29			
30	08:44:00	44:30			slightly hazy.
054	08:46:00	46:30			
489 451	08:48:00	48:29			
183	08:50:00	50:29			
046	08:52:00	52:27			profile to 50 feet
045	08:54:00	54:30			standard
043	08:58:00	58:30			10.2 °C
250	9:00:00	4:00:29			
022	9:02:00	02:30			
0245	9:04:11	04:30			at 70 feet
122	04:44	05:13			at 100 feet
545	9:05:56	06:21			start climb to 500 feet
436	9:07:07	07:36			at 500 feet
085	9:08:14	08:42			climb to 2000
089	09:08	09:30			
518	09:52	09:10:21			2000 feet standard
24	10:54	11:24			profile climb to 4000
79	10:43	12:11			
557	13:00	13:30			start num
78	14:00	14:30			
4	14:46	15:16			in cloud.
80	16:02	16:32			6000 feet
285	18:30	19:00			"
73	21:00	21:30			"
124	24:30	25:00			"
	25:00	25:30			

run 1
start
at
1000 feetrun land
almost
at point
37end of
profile

Flight No. 13102Route

England/Willy

Date 14-06-05Take Off Bag Samplers: Ute DebyeSheet No. 2

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
282	09:27:00	09:27:00			6000 feet
83	09:29:30	09:29:57			
185	30:25	09:30:00	5300	5800	profile to 1000 feet
190	31:30	32:00	4300	3700	
290	32:30	33:00		2800	
424	33:30	34:00		1700	
370	34:30	34:57	1200	1000	end of profile.
27	36:00	36:25	1000 feet		large CO peak.
353	38:00	38:30			
457	09:40:00	40:30			plume of NOx SO2
271	09:42:00	42:30			
363	09:44:00	44:30			
011	09:46:00	46:30			
184	09:48:00	48:30			
077	09:50:00	50:30			Isle of Wights
308	09:52:00	09:52:30			
552	09:54:00	09:54:30			
38	09:56:00	56:30			
203	09:58:00	58:30			
426	10:00:00	10:00:30			
520	10:02:00	10:02:30			
072	10:04:05	10:04:35			
172	10:06:00	10:06:30			
342	10:08:00	10:08:30			end of run to point H3
318	09:10:00	09:30			
293	10:00	10:30			CO plume.
496	10:00	11:30			
439	12:00	12:30			
016	13:00	13:30			
555	14:00	14:30			
214	15:00	15:30			
015	16:00	16:30			
012	17:00	17:30			
003	18:00	18:30			
178	19:00	19:30			ships Dover (daisy) straits
041	20:00	20:00			
558	21:00	21:30			
253	22:00	22:30			
37	23:00	23:30			
288	24:00	24:00			
245	25:00	25:30			turbulence.

Wind
10ms⁻¹

started

visible

end of run.

H3

straits

End of run
7

Flight No. Route Date Take Off Bag Samplers: Sheet No.

1000 feet.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
498	10:26:00	10:26:30			
175	27:00	27:30			
517	28:00	28:30			
359	29:00	29:30			Bag is damaged.
28	30:00	30:30			
551	10:30:00	31:30			
314	32:00	32:30			
123	33:00	33:30			leaded point 41 end of run 8
80	34:00	34:30			CO release
241	35:00	35:30			NOx SO ₂
26	36:00	36:30			
255	37:00	37:30			
177	38:00	38:30			CO / NOx release.
40	39:00	39:30			
23	40:00	40:30			low Sulfur.
39	41:00	41:30			SO ₂ sharp peak
455	42:00	42:30			
411	43:00	43:30			
52	44:00	44:30			
49	45:00	45:30			
470	46:00	46:30			end of run 9
70	47:00	47:30			
59	48:00	48:30			big CO peak
68	49:00	49:30			
10	50:00	50:30			
181	51:00	51:30			low Sulfur.
74	52:00	52:30			"
402	53:00	53:30			"
067	54:00	54:30			Crowder
425	55:00	55:30			
249	56:00	56:30			Bag did not fill much
415	57:00	57:30			
430	58:00	58:30			
247	59:00	59:30			
61	11:00:00	11:00:30			
9	11:01:00	01:30			
126	02:00	02:30			
62	03:00	03:30			
13	04:00	04:30			
129	05:00	05:30			
001	06:00	06:30			

with 7ms

32

run 10

end of run 10
point 87
87-80
run 11

Flight No. 13102Route Date 14:6:05Take Off Bag Samplers: Wt DobbleSheet No. 4

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
002	11:07:00	11:07:30			1000 feet
435	11:08:00	11:08:30			mouth of Hudson
252	11:09:00		Downriver	Grimsby	SO ₂ NO _x plume
524	11:10:00	11:10:30			
493	11:11:00	11:11:30			
21	12:00	12:30			
403	13:00	13:30			
007	14:00	14:30			peak of NO _x SO ₂
176	15:00	15:30			
244	16:00	16:30			
127	17:00	17:30			
173	18:00	18:30			start of run 12
511	19:00	19:30			rise in NO _x plume
56	20:00	20:30			
5	21:00	21:30			1200 feet
53	22:00	22:30			SO ₂ NO _x plume
55	23:00	23:30			"
256	24:00	24:30			"
272	25:00	25:30			"
454	26:00	26:30			"
232	27:00	27:30			" well defined CO peak
402	28:00	28:30			
17	29:00	29:30			
64	30:00	30:30			
186	31:00	31:30			not well SO ₂
90	32:00	32:30			
189	33:00	-30			
82	34:00	-30			
75	35:00	-30			
499	36:00	-30			
87	37:00	-30			
6	38:00	-30			(CO + NO _x SO ₂) plume
30	39:00	-30			
84	40:00	-30			
128	41:00	-30			
86	42:00	-30			
58	43:00	-30			
66	44:00	-30			
69	45:00	-30			plume of NO _x
57	46:00	-30			" Holy Island
071	47:00	-30			

end of run 80

Flamewall head

} turbulent

Flight No. 13102Route Date 14.6.05Take Off Bag Samplers: Use D & S 1/2Sheet No. 5

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
65	11:48:00	11:48:30			end of run 12
60	11:49:00	11:49:30			climb to 5000 feet
descent to Newcastle now.					
To Newcastle 13:37					
626	13:43:00	13:43:30			6000 ft
610	13:50:00	13:50:30			5000 ft
611	13:51:00	13:51:30			6000 ft level
612	13:52:00	13:52:30			5000 → 4000 (500)
613	13:53:00	13:53:30			4000
97	13:54:00	13:54:30			4000
614	13:55:00	13:55:30			4000
615	13:55:45	13:56:15	55°N	1.6W	4000 → 2000 (300)
616	13:56:40	13:57:10			~2000
617	13:57:45	13:58:15			2000
618	13:58:55	13:59:25			~1800
619	14:00:00	14:00:30			~800
620	14:01:00	14:01:30			~500
622	14:01:40	14:02:10			@ 100
623	14:02:40	14:03:10			100 → 500 (*)
624	14:03:30	14:04:00	3W	20°E	@ 500
625	14:04:30	14:05:00			500 → 1000 (800)
621	14:05:20	14:05:50			1000 ft.
95	14:06:20	14:06:50			1000 ft.
98	14:07:20	14:08:00			"
133	14:08:30	14:09:00		5W/8	20°E
132	14:09:20	14:10:00			"
99	14:10:30	14:11:00			"
100	14:11:30	14:12:00	55.0	1.1W	"
91	14:12:30	14:13:00			rain to the west
92	14:13:30	14:14:00			@ PT 79
92	14:14:30	14:15:00			
162	14:15:30	14:16:00			
31	14:16:30	14:17:00			
32	14:17:30	14:18:00			Chinese started to west
161	14:18:30	14:19:00			
86	14:19:30	14:20:00			Chimney upwind
140	14:20:30	14:21:00			
117	14:21:30	14:22:00			
113	14:22:30	14:23:00			
101	14:23:30	14:24:00			
102	14:24:30	14:25:00			1000 ft

in cloud
PRSwest
cement?
→ no
plume
detected

Flight No. Route Date Take Off Bag Samplers: Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
8-103	14:25:30	14:26:00	54.3	0.3 W	1000 ft
104	14:26:30	14:27:00			
104	14:27:30	14:28:00			
106	14:28:30	14:29:00			
108	14:29:30	14:30:00			
107	14:30:30	14:31:00	233°	13 w/s	NOx plume - not very faint
119	14:31:30	14:32:00			@ FT 30
114	14:32:30	14:33:00			
115	14:33:30	14:34:00			
116	14:34:30	14:35:00			Phil elevated 150
117	14:35:30	14:36:00			
118	14:36:30	14:37:00			
109	14:37:30	14:38:00			Ship below
111	14:38:30	14:39:00			
105	14:39:30	14:40:00			
110	14:40:30	14:41:00			
151	14:41:30	14:42:00			
152	14:42:30	14:43:00	53.34	0.5 E	all @ 1000 ft
139	14:43:30	14:44:00			
135	14:44:30	14:45:00			
136	14:45:30	14:46:00			
137	14:46:30	14:47:00			
138	14:47:30	14:48:00			
134	14:48:30	14:49:00			
153	14:49:30	14:50:00			
154	14:50:30	14:51:00	235°	9 w/s	@ 87
155	14:51:30	14:52:00			
156	14:52:30	14:52:00			
600	14:53:30	14:54:00			
601	14:54:30	14:55:00			
603	14:55:30	14:56:00			
609	14:56:30	14:57:00			
608	14:57:30	14:58:00			
607	14:58:30	14:59:00			
602	14:59:30	15:00:00			
606	15:00:30	15:01:00			
605	15:01:30	15:02:00			
604	15:02:30	15:03:00			@ FT 40
157	15:03:30	15:04:00			
158	15:04:30	15:05:00			
159	15:05:30	15:06:00			

elevated
 NOx & CO
 no SO₂
 ⇒ London
 plume?

Flight No. 2102Route Date 14/06/05Take Off Bag Samplers: Wibie & ElioSheet No. 7

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05-16a	15:06:30	15:07:00	52.4N	1.8E	NOx & CO plane
629	15:07:30	15:08:00			"
627	15:08:30	15:09:00			"
628	15:09:30	15:10:00			end of plane
33	15:10:30	15:11:00			
24	15:11:30	15:12:00			
25	15:12:30	15:13:00			
96	15:13:30	15:14:00			
377	15:14:30	15:15:00			
278	15:15:30	15:16:00			wt v. full
344	15:16:30	15:17:00	51.3	236°	@ PT43
284	15:17:30	15:18:00			
354	15:18:30	15:19:00			
352	15:19:30	15:20:00			
378	15:20:30	15:21:00			
28a	15:21:30	15:22:00			
174	15:22:30	15:23:00			
37c	15:23:30	15:24:00	51.5N	1.6E	
350	15:24:30	15:25:00			
379	15:25:30	15:26:00			
164	15:26:30	15:27:00			
461	15:27:30	15:28:00			
141	15:28:30	15:29:00			
143	15:29:30	15:30:00			
525	15:30:30	15:31:00			
166	15:31:30	15:32:00			
163	15:32:30	15:33:00			@ PT42
146	15:33:30	15:34:00			
145	15:34:30	15:35:00			
170	15:35:30	15:36:00			
559	15:36:30	15:37:00			
142	15:37:30	15:38:00			
453	15:38:30	15:39:00			
10	15:39:30	15:40:00			
147	15:40:30	15:41:00	51.3	1.5E	
old 252/262	15:41:30	15:42:00			End of Run
05-168	15:43:30	15:48:00			↑ all @ 1000
428	15:43:35	15:46:05		@ 400	1000 → 2000
149	15:46:35	15:46:55		100 → 500	
438	15:47:05	15:47:40		@ 500	
317	15:48:20	15:48:55		500 → 2000	(N 700)

1000 ft

elevated NOx

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:	B118	Date:	03 Aug 2005	Operator:	Doug Anderson
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Run No	Disk No 1	Disk No 2	Disk No 3	Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
	TOP	MIDDLE	BOTTOM						
Transit	113	91	155	Top	10:14:10	11:00:20	Transit	(10?)121 or 721	Background (transit) Acc Vol is lower than early in run if 3 digit value taken hence question marked 10 (four digit display!) Previously Top was 2/3 value of Bottom 721 : misread top – due to viewing from too high an angle?
Transit	117	140	120	Bottom	10:14:10	11:00:20	transit	(10?)830	Background (transit)
Filters run1	159	No #	58	Top	11:18:54	11:50:35	R6	645	Few ml water on top of filter when taken out after 30 min
Filters run1	153	143	92	Bottom	11:18:54	11:50:35	R6	957 (since 11:25:40)	Bottom display zero button jammed in. Zero flow measured until released 11:25:40
Filters run2	132	139	5	Top	11:55:45	12:25:20	R6	567	
Filters run2	53	123	141	Bottom	11:55:45	12:25:20	R6	1226	
Filters run3	112	150	84	Top	12:28:50	12:58:50	R6	473	
Filters run3	114	93	156	Bottom	12:28:50	12:58:50	R6	1093	
Filters run4	148	97	18	Top	13:01:35	13:28:35	R6	505	
Filters run4	152	85	54	Bottom	13:01:35	13:28:35	R6	852	
Filters run5	87	145	10	Top	13:44:12	14:20:30	R10	595	
Filters run5	134	94	116	Bottom	13:44:12	14:20:30	R10	1158	
transit home	90	157	125	Top	14:28:00	14:41:35	N/a	100	Sample pipes were open so not a blank run
transit home	No #	146	98	Bottom	14:28:00	14:41:35	N/a	242	Sample pipes were open so not a blank run
				Top					
				Bottom					
				Top					
				Bottom					
				Top					
				Bottom					

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 3/8/05

FLIGHT: B118

OPERATOR: GC

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Power ON	Ensure Inlet Closed	Inlet Valve	✓		
	Ensure Multiplier Off	Electronics box	✓		
	Ensure Heater Off	Electronics box	✓		
	Ensure all Pumps Off	Pump Control box	✓		
	Turn on 230V Breaker	Power unit on a/c wall	✓		
	Turn on: Electronics box power Diaphragm pump power Turbo pump power CPC Power, both Buttons	Power distribution box	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓		
	Open backing pump valve	Front facing side of rack.	✓		
	Turn on Alcatel...100% speed	Pump Control Box, after #6	✓	Monitor Pump Currents	
	Turbo pumps 2 and 3 ON...100%	Pump Control Box	✓		
	Turbo pumps 4 and 5 ON...100%	Pump Control Box	✓		
	Turbo pump 6 ON...100%	Pump Control Box	✓		
	Plug in CPC fill bottle	Rear of CPC	✓		
Turn on heater	Electronics box	✓		Approx 2.8V, 0.9A	
Pre-Brief	Turn on Balzers Box	Power distribution box and Balzers box	✓		
	Turn on Copper	Electronics box	✓		Approx 125Hz
	Turn on PC/Monitor	Power distribution box and PC	✓		
	Start AMS software	PC Desktop	✓		
	Turn autosaving off	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		NEGATIVE NUMBER
	Reduce Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓		
	Set filament to 0.00mA, Scan range 0-300amu	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Turn Multiplier on	Electronics box	✓		
	Turn filament on @0.05mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓		

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 3/8/05

FLIGHT: B118

OPERATOR: GC

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Post Brief	Increase Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓		
	Close Grimm valve	Inlet valve	✓		
	CPC in low flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	Check RF box, Tune if needed	Turn Tune Screw on RF Box for best hit	✓		
	Log CPC on AMS serial port 2	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Open AMS inlet	Inlet valve	✓		
	Increase filament to 2.5mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emmission arrow	✓		
	Toggle chopper in MS mode	Press T within MS mode	✓		
	Check Airbeams and flows	Add m28 to m/z selection, Clean pin hole???	✓	F=1.9,AB approx 2.3MHz	✓
	Tune Balzers	Software	✓	Ensure no major changes	✓
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓	Gain approx 3e6	2.5e6
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓	15,16,17,30,46*	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓	wait	
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓	Check tof windows	
	IE cal after 200 particules	Shift+M while sampling, Calibrate, Save, Exit	✓	SMPS s=4.1, a=0.41, 350nm	
	Remove CPC butanol from aircraft	Rear of CPC	✓		
	CPC in high flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	Reconnect inlet and GRIMM	Inlet	✓		
	Set CPC port=0 in AMS software	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓	LOG CPC IN LABVIEW	
	Set PC time with Horace	Desktop plus internet explorer	✓		
	Set mass range scan	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Select tof masses to scan	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓	14,16,30,43,44,46,48,57	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓		
	Set DC marker 3 pos=6200	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		
	Backup parameter file	C:\AMSVAMSCODE\AMSMMenu.prm	✓		
	Set save interval	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓	0.5 minutes????	
Reconnect inlet, Close AMS valve	Inlet	✓			
Start CPC software	PC Desktop	✓			
General Alteration mode, Open Inlet	Software, Start after t/o	✓			

AMS Calibration Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 3/8/05 FLIGHT: B118

OPERATOR: GC

Tuning

Post flight

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner			22
Def Outer			11
Heater Bias			-6.5
Focus			12.5
Extraction			220

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner	30	30	22
Def Outer	15	15	11
Heater Bias	-6.68	-6.49	-6.5
Focus	15.00	15.00	12.5
Extraction	230	226	220

Pre flight

Multiplier Cal

Might have to tweak filament current and multiplier voltage in order to set thresholds in calibration!!!!
This is done in the parameter menu..... Multiplier and Chopper Tab

TIME:	New	Typical
KV	2.475	n/a
KV Change	0.025	0.025kV
Gain	2.96	3.00E+06
G used Change	1.01	1

TIME:	New	Typical
KV	2.475	n/a
KV Change	0.025	0.025kV
Gain	2.93	3.00E+06
G used Change	0.84	1

2.450
-0.050

Ionization Efficiency Cal

TIME:	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	2.521	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	3.656	4
IPP NO3	586	400
IPP NH4	622	550
Airbeam MS	2.53	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	1.24	2.00E+06
Run Number	4467	n/a

TIME:	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	1.614	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	3.554	4
IPP NO3	395	400
IPP NH4	387	550
Airbeam MS	2.18	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	1.34	2.00E+06
Run Number	2	n/a

Filter Run

TIME:	14:30
Run number	4424

TIME:	10:12
Run number	3932

AMS Diagnostic Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 3/8/05 FLIGHT: B118

OPERATOR: GC

← pre-flight →

Time 10:35

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.78	0.86	86	98
2	2.99	3.5	100	100
3	1.32	1	100	100
4	0.59	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.46	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.81	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	584	580
Heater B	73.1	75V
Multiplier	2.45	n/a
Pressure	1.46	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	7	7A
I diaphragm	1.4	2A
MS AB	2.19	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	2.05	2Mhz
Flow	1.92	2

Time 11:20

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.89	0.86	86	98
2	3.44	3.5	100	100
3	1.35	1	100	100
4	0.60	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.46	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.82	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	588	580
Heater B	73.1	75V
Multiplier	2.44	n/a
Pressure	1.86	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	7	7A
I diaphragm	1.4	2A
MS AB	2.31	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	2.05	2Mhz
Flow	2.08	2

Time 12:30

no significant change 13:30

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.90	0.86	90	98
2	3.45	3.5	100	100
3	1.38	1	100	100
4	0.59	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.46	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.82	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	589	580
Heater B	73.1	75V
Multiplier	1.86	n/a
Pressure	2.44	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1.0	1A
I turbo	7.5	7A
I diaphragm	1.4	2A
MS AB	2.32	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	2.07	2Mhz
Flow	2.07	2

Time 14:35

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.73	0.86	86	98
2	2.85	3.5	100	100
3	1.27	1	100	100
4	0.60	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.43	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.82	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	589	580
Heater B	73.1	75V
Multiplier	2.44	n/a
Pressure	1.35	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1.0	1A
I turbo	7	7A
I diaphragm	1.4	2A
MS AB	1.74	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	1.56	2Mhz
Flow	1.34	2

AMS PostFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 3/8/05

FLIGHT: B118

OPERATOR: GC

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Pre-land	Stop AMS,Grimm CPC logging	Software	✓		
	Close AMS inlet	Inlet	✓		
	Exit Labview		✓		
	Enable CPC in AMS software	Parameter Menu, Serial Ports tab	✓		
Post-land	Set CPC in Low Flow	Shift+totalizer on CPC display	✓		
	Open Inlet		✓		
	Turn off autosave (-ve number)	Parameter Menu,Averaging and saving tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓	Check gain at current V	
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓	15,16,17,30,46*	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓	wait	
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓	Check tof windows	
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling,Calibrate,Save.Exit	✓	SMPS s=4.1,a=0.41,350nm	
	Attach Zero filter to inlet		x		
	Select tof masses to scan	Software,mz selection,left click on row	x	14,16,30,43,44,46,48,57	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	x		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software,mz selection,left click on row	x		
	General alteration,10 mins	Software, F3 to NonAutoSave	x	Check tof windows	
	Close inlet		✓		
Data	Copy AutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy NonAutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\NonAutoSaveDate	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy AMSLogFiles folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AMSLogFiles	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy CPC data	Source C:\UCPC\	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Backup directory to DVD/laptop		✓		
	Delete AutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
Delete NonAutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER		
Delete AMSLogFiles	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER		
Delete CPC data	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER		
ShutDown	Turn off Multplier & Balzers	Electronics box	✓		
	Turn off all Turbos and PC	Pump Controller Box	✓		
	Shut Backing Valve	Back of rack	✓		
	Turn off heater,chopper,the rest	Electronics box, then power unit and Breakers	✓		

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B118**

Date: 03/08/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	Y	Y
Heimann	N		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	Y
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	N
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	N
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	N
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B118

Date: 03/08/05

Instruments

1. Meths - spray bottle missing from chemical cupboard in 125 Lab pre-flight.
2. SO₂ – Mains connector not making contact with the SO₂ on pre-flight. Pushed it in than okay. Needs some foam or similar in between connector and back-stop.
3. CCNC Rack - padding on aisle side falling off.
4. AMS – Ammonium Nitrate crystals dropped on floor by rack pre-flight. Mopped up with water and tissues.

Status of other instruments

CPI –
Cloud Physics –
NO_x – ok
CVI - ok

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom H Calls -

EGTC -> EGSC - Overview

NavData Cycle 2005-7 Expires: Thursday, 04 August 2005.

Scale: 1:2451710 (1 inch = 33.62 naut mi). Printed on 02 Aug 2005

JEPPESEN

FliteStar 9.130

Tephi take-off:

New plot, same times

Flight B118 10:34:31
Heading 258 deg Speed 267 knots Height 10.0kft Press 696mb
Lat 51.8N Long 2.5W Wind 19 ms-1/ 295 deg
Temp -2.58C Dewpoint -13.29C
From start to now

Current values
— TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 38070 secs All scroll time
— DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP 270.57 K
— CNC COUNTS 1030 p cm-3

Tehpi graph Cornwall upwind profile

Wind direction change during upwind profile and just after:

Sea breeze effect SE:

New plot, same times

Flight B118 13:00:50
Heading 322 deg Speed 219 knots Height 0.7kft Press 985mb
Lat 53.9N Long 0.1E Wind 11 ms-1/274 deg
Temp 16.23C Dewpoint 6.2C
From start to now

Current values
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 46848 secs
INS WIND ANGLE 274.97 deg

All sc

Tephigraph downwind (Newcastle)

New plot, same times

Flight B118 13:53:44
Heading 158 deg Speed 206 knots Height 0.8kft Press 982mb
Lat 54.0N Long 0.1E Wind 13 ms-1/266 deg
Temp 15.51C Dewpoint 8.24C
From start to now

Current values
— TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 50022 secs All scroll time
— DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP 288.68 K
— CNC COUNTS 27600 p cm-3

Flight B118 14:25:38
Heading 271 deg Speed 238 knots Height 6.1kft Press 808mb
Lat 52.6N Long 1.5E Wind 8 ms-1/ 299 deg
Temp 3.61C Dewpoint -0.77C
From start to now

Current values
INU LATITUDE 52.66 deg (+ve N) All
INS WIND ANGLE 299.96 deg

Flight B118 14:26:48
Heading 274 deg Speed 251 knots Height 9.4kft Press 711mb
Lat 52.6N Long 1.4E Wind 10 ms-1/285 deg
Temp -3.08C Dewpoint -8.05C
From start to now

Current values
INU LONGITUDE 1.48 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
INU LATITUDE 52.66 deg (+ve N)

Flight B118 14:28:54
Heading 273 deg Speed 232 knots Height 9.9kft Press 697mb
Lat 52.6N Long 1.2E Wind 13 ms-1/294 deg
Temp -5.25C Dewpoint -7.13C
From 13:58:38 to now

Current values
STATIC PRESSURE 697.23 mb
DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP -5.25 deg C
DEW POINT -7.14 deg C